

SOCIAL SCIENCES

FEATURES OF INTEGRATION OF THE RUSSIAN SYSTEM OF HIGHER EDUCATION INTO THE BOLOGNA PROCESS

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Abstract

The article analyzes the validity of stable statements about the consequences of the ratification of the Bologna Declaration in Russia, which turned out to be myths, shows the real situation in this area and ways to reform the domestic system of higher education in the framework of following the Bologna process.

Keywords: Bologna Declaration, Bologna process, higher education reforms.

Introduction. Russia joined the Bologna system, widely known in the university environment, in November 2003. This caused heated debate, misunderstanding, and internal resistance from several teachers [1]; others, on the contrary, consistently supported the adopted decision [2, 81]. More than 12 years have passed since that moment, allowing a less emotional approach to the assessment of this innovation, still surrounded by myths and half-truths.

On April 11, 2022, against the background of the deterioration of relations between Russia and Western countries, the Bologna Group announced a decision to stop the representation of Russia and Belarus in all structures of the Bologna process. In May 2022, the intention of the Russian Federation to withdraw from the Bologna process was announced.

However, the announced withdrawal from the Bologna process does not imply a categorical rejection of those of its elements that have already taken root in the Russian Federation. A specific part of the Bologna system is currently being discussed most actively in Russia, namely the principle of dividing higher education into bachelor's and master's programs.

Discussion. The first myth is that the Bologna Declaration was signed during the heyday of European universities in the Middle Ages. The Bologna system that emerged at the end of the 20th century is a natural result of European countries' economic and political integration.

The Bologna Declaration was signed relatively recently - June 19, 1999. This was by no means due to the growing scientific influence of European universities but to the technical need to unify countries' education systems in connection with significant progress in the organization of the European Union.

The name of the declaration – “European Higher Education Area”, taken from the Sorbonne Declaration (signed on May 25, 1998), fully reflects its essence: the creation of this zone is “a key way to develop the mobility of citizens with the possibility of their employment for the general development of the continent” [3].

Without a doubt, close economic and political integration in Europe is impossible without “adopting a system of easily understood and comparable degrees” [3]. In this regard, the intensification of diplomatic efforts in this direction occurred at the final stage of the creation of the European Union.

The second myth is more complicated since some experts believe that reforming the Russian higher education system is impossible without joining the Bologna process. However, in reality, we saw that similar innovations could be carried out without the ratification of the Bologna Declaration.

In the short text of the Bologna Declaration, only the general principles of “promotion of the European system of higher education around the world” are indicated [3]:

- 1) Formation of a two-stage system of higher education; the duration of the development of the first part is at least three years;
- 2) Streamlining the titles of awarded degrees (for example, in France instead of a bachelor's degree, a licentiate degree was awarded), the introduction of an international Diploma Supplement;
- 3) Introduction of a credit system (ECTS - European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System²) to take into account the complexity of mastering individual disciplines;
- 4) The goal is to facilitate the transfer of students to other universities in determining the level of

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² In Russia, this is 36 academic hours (27 astronomical hours) for lectures, seminars, self-training, etc.

their training; promotion of academic mobility of students and teachers, as well as several other measures.

All of the above, except for the first point, contribute to improving the quality of higher education in any country. The introduction of these principles in Russia was possible even without the ratification of the Bologna Declaration since the latter entailed a painful rejection of the “Soviet” five-year scheme of higher education³. The ratification that took place also had a positive impact on the image. However, it quickly faded away, because, apart from the formal “division” of the specialty into two parts (bachelor's and master's), in fact, nothing.⁴

The third myth concerns the “inherited” Soviet higher education system, considering it fundamental and not needing Bologna innovations. The reality is this: the modern Russian system of higher education needs serious reforms, including those based on the Bologna system.

The need to reform the modern Russian system of higher education is beyond doubt [4]. This is evidenced by both the persistent subjective, i.e., unproven, opinion about the total low level of knowledge of modern graduates of Russian universities and much more significant results of state monitoring of the effectiveness of universities (Table 1).

Table 1.

Some information about the results of monitoring the effectiveness of Russian universities in 2014

Monitoring result	Total	Head office	Branch
Achieved <4 indicators	162*	27	135
	40**	32	8
Achieved >4 indicators	843*	487	356
	208**	137	71
Other (reorganization, additional checks, etc.)	311*	18	293
	568**	199	369
Reference:			
Share of problem institutions, %	35,94*	8,46	54,59
Monitoring result	74,51**	62,77	84,15

Source: RF Ministry of Education and Science [4], author's calculations.

Note: * - state; ** - non-state.

As can be seen from Table 1, more than a third of state universities and their branches are problematic; the same indicator among private establishments is catastrophic - three quarters. Of course, the question of the objectivity of the criteria used by the Ministry of Education and Science is debatable, however, like any rating technique. However, Russian universities do not occupy leading positions in international rankings either. This is not catastrophic, more important is the significant scale of the problems that require immediate and, most likely, painful solutions.

Let's consider another myth, according to which students and teachers of Russian universities have academic mobility. Reality shows the lack of academic mobility due to certain objective conditions.

In Europe, the issue of potential academic mobility is easier to solve: as a rule, knowledge of at least three languages (English, French, German) is common. Despite the strong conviction of post-Soviet Russians that their domestic education is one of the best in the world, the knowledge of Russian schoolchildren in the field of foreign languages is usually modest: English or German, less often

French, and even then without proper practice. The reasons are by no means in the superiority of foreign teenagers over Russians - these European languages are included in the same Germanic group, which greatly facilitates their assimilation. In addition, the acquisition of practical language skills by foreign students is simplified as much as possible, since the countries are close neighbors, the cost of living in them is approximately the same. Based on this, the majority of Russian students objectively do not need academic mobility and the opportunity to study at European universities - they do not have a high level of language proficiency to understand foreign professors, and they do not have the means to make long-distance voyages, especially in the context of a sharp devaluation of the ruble.

Unfortunately, the same can be said about a significant part (if not the majority) of university professors. Their fluency in English (not to mention other languages) was not in demand, especially in the recent past, when wages were at a very low level.

Intra-Russian academic mobility (to leading national research universities) is limited by the lack of dormitories (Table 2).

³ In some cases, for example in medicine, it is longer (6 years and residency/internship).

⁴ Vivid videos about illiterate graduates who do not know that Erich Maria Remarque is a man, that Lermontov shot with Martynov, and the Volga flows into the Caspian Sea,

etc., do not prove anything at all. Their purpose is to create the desired emotional background. With the same success, based on the program “Clever Boys and Girls”, one can draw opposite conclusions. The reasons for incorrect conclusions are unrepresentative samples of subjects [8].

Table 2.

Some information about the provision of university students with dormitories in 2009-2011

Index		2019	2020	2021
Total number of students (as of September 1)		3 457	3 280	3 073
Students in need of a hostel (at the end of the year)		947,8	932,8	1 040,3
Of which lives in a hostel	%	813,2	808,7	829,1
		85,8	86,7	79,7
Living area per student, m ²		7,7	7,8	7,7
Reference:				
Living space per student (non-state universities), m ²		8,1	9,4	11,6
Needy and not provided with a hostel	thousand people	134,6	124,1	211,2
	mln m ²	1,04	0,97	1,63
	% of total	3,89	3,78	6,87

Source: author's calculations.

As can be seen from Table. 2, more than 210 thousand students (7%) are unable to obtain affordable housing; the size of the missing fund is comparable to the annual volume of new housing construction in Novosibirsk (1.46 million m² in 2014 [5]). Even without taking into account the very small area per student (≥ 8 m², where you need to place a bed, a table, and a wardrobe!), it is worth emphasizing that the quality of repairs, the sanitary condition of university dormitories do not always meet the standards [5].

All this significantly limits the possibilities of intra-Russian academic mobility for both students and teachers. The main reasons are the first - the lack of a legislative framework for the transfer of disciplines studied in other universities, despite the introduction of credit units; the second is material factors.

The fifth myth concerns the recognition of Russian diplomas in foreign countries, in case of joining the Bologna system. The current reality is this: no "international appendices" to Russian documents on higher education will replace the need for a procedure for their recognition in specific foreign countries.

The Bologna Declaration does not contain a word about the recognition of foreign diplomas. This issue is regulated by the "Lisbon Convention on the Recognition of Qualifications Relating to Higher Education in the European Region", of 11 April 1997. It is often included in the Bologna Process, but the number of countries that have ratified the Bologna Declaration is less than those that have also ratified the Lisbon Convention.

According to Art. VI.1 of the Lisbon Convention, "each Party shall recognize higher education qualifications issued in the other Party unless significant differences between the qualifications can be reasonably presented." It would seem that everything is extremely simple, but in practice documents on education must be submitted to specially created national information centers that provide consulting support and/or through authorized organizations to carry out the procedure for recognizing diplomas. In Russia, this is the FGBU "Glavexpertcenter", in India, the Association of Indian Universities, and in France, the International Center for Education. It is worth noting that, for example, in the UK, the deci-

sion of the National Information Center "is recommended; educational institutions, professional associations, and employers independently decide on the admission of holders of foreign documents on education and qualifications to work or study. In the USA, the procedure is not legally regulated; recognition is carried out by educational institutions, professional associations, etc.

Thus, no Diploma Supplement in the form of UNESCO within the Bologna system is the basis for the recognition of Russian diplomas abroad.

The sixth myth has developed in the form of the belief that the Bologna Declaration establishes a longer duration of education than was customary in Russia. The Bologna Declaration establishes the minimum duration of study for the bachelor's degree, and for the master's degree, it does not regulate at all.

In Russia, five-year education in universities is traditionally accepted. The Bologna Declaration establishes a minimum period of study for a bachelor's degree of three years. For example, at Oxford University, the duration of study is only three years; a master's degree takes only one year. The total period of obtaining a "complete" higher education corresponds to the "bachelor's level" in Russia. At other universities, such as Cambridge, a bachelor's degree takes 3-4 years to complete, while a master's degree in some areas takes up to two years. Traditionally, in several medical areas, the training period is longer - 5-6 years.

In 2003, as well as the next few years, there was an opinion that the introduction of the Bologna system would lead to the release of undereducated specialists in Russia. But here everyone preferred to forget that the Soviet experience spoke of the sufficiency of four years of higher education for several areas.

The persistent opinion that with the transition to a four-year education, bachelor students do not have the opportunity to listen to a full course of lectures for specialists, is not entirely true.

Firstly, the time difference is not so significant and is only one semester, not two, as it seems at first glance. Bachelors in the 4th year, as well as specialists, study for two semesters (the second is shortened by two months, required for writing a final work).

Specialists studied for one more full-fledged semester in the 5th year, and the remaining six months slowly went through practice and wrote theses.

Secondly, in the Soviet past, training in all economic specialties at the institutes of the national economy was carried out in four years due to a balanced training program that excluded duplication of disciplines, "superfluous" subjects, etc. Although it also included "History of Communist Party", "Marxist-Leninist Ethics and Aesthetics", and "Scientific Communism", etc. Perhaps, for several areas of training (primarily medical) four years is not enough, however, we recall that in Oxford they manage to do this in three years (True, future doctors study longer - six years). No one in the world doubts the qualifications of bachelor graduates of this educational institution.

Let's look at another misconception. In particular, the belief that the newly introduced magistracy institute increases the degree of students' preparation for the "Soviet" specialty. In fact, in several cases, for objective reasons, the level of training of masters is lower than that of specialists and even bachelors.[7]

The first cut of the problem. The Institute of Masters as an element of the system of higher education within the framework of the Bologna process allows for obtaining a variety of qualifications. For example, after receiving a bachelor's degree in aircraft engineering, you can enroll in a master's program in economics or law (or vice versa).⁵

Theoretically, all bachelors should retain knowledge in general subjects - history, higher mathematics, etc. But, unfortunately, "non-core" undergraduates usually do not have a highly specialized base, a theoretical foundation.⁶

According to paragraph 6 of Article 69 of the Law "On Education in the Russian Federation" "Admission to study at a master's program <...> is carried out based on the results of entrance examinations conducted by the educational organization itself." The ease of commercial admission to the magistracy of many universities de facto distorts the meaning of the Bologna Declaration. This allows "non-core" bachelors to use the master's program as an easy way to get the "necessary" higher education in a short time (two years).

The second section of the problem. The volume of study in the master's program is much lower than

in the bachelor's degree; classes are usually held in the evenings and intensively on Saturdays (so that undergraduates can combine work with study). It is worth recalling that with the introduction of 11-year school education, undergraduates are no longer children, they are already 22-25 years old. The working day ends at 18:00, so the first lectures (at 16:50) are usually skipped. And if you start training at 18-30, then the classes will end too late - at 21-30. In addition, the general fatigue of students and the lack of free time objectively impede the assimilation of subjects and self-training.

The third section of the problem. Although undergraduates formally prepare for scientific and teaching activities, most graduates will not do this. Why, then, study a large number of philosophical and "near-philosophical" disciplines?

For a very long time, university specialists have argued that it is impossible to reform the higher education system within the framework of the Bologna Declaration; a return to the "Soviet" system is necessary. The Bologna system defines "a great variety of education systems in the European Region <...>, which requires every respect", i. e. nothing prevents the modernization of the system of higher education in Russia.⁷

The problem is not Russia's accession to the Bologna system, but how to "adapt" the educational process to the new conditions. The current situation is rightly criticized by many, but it is by no means hopeless, in connection with which the author sees several basic steps to improve it.

Step 1: Active introduction of the abbreviated applied baccalaureate as a replacement for the programs of a significant part of secondary specialized educational institutions. To what extent is higher education in demand in Russia? Of those studying in general education schools, 86% of people aged 15 years and older plan to continue their education, of which 77.3% - are in universities. In most cases, their intentions are put into practice: in 2020 they were 45.6%, in 2021 - 51.2%, and in 2022 - 61.7%.

Young people want to have a higher education - that's a fact. So why should they be able to? In addition to image considerations, this aspiration of young people is also dictated by objective reasons - lower unemployment and higher wages for specialists with higher education (Fig.1).

⁵ According to paragraph 3 of Art. 69 of Law No. 273-FZ "On Education in the Russian Federation" of December 29, 2012, "Persons with higher education of any level are allowed to master the master's programs."

⁶ For example, the author can hardly imagine his studies in the magistracy of the Novosibirsk State University in the direction of "Mechanics and Mathematical Modeling" or "Physics".

⁷ Cit. under the Lisbon Convention of 11 April. 1997

Average accrued wages of employees by levels of education, 2018–2022, thousand rubles

Source: Rosstat, Education [8].

Taking into account the minimum possible period of study of three years, it is necessary to reduce the study of general university disciplines (for example, to 1–2 semesters), devoting maximum time (2–2.5 years) to practical professions. With a mandatory degree from a compulsory 11-year school program, having received a fairly broad professional education, including in the “general cultural” field, and professional skills, and acquaintance with higher education subjects, as a result, he must be a qualified master specialist - bachelor with applied research.

Step 2: Reworking and intensifying the “classic” bachelor's programs. It is necessary to conduct a social scientific examination of advanced training, excluding these disciplines from them, without high-quality training, which is unlikely to suffer⁸. The action needs to be developed together with relevant organizations. For example, work programs for training economists in the field of banking, the securities market, and guarantees must be coordinated with the Bank of Russia, “Rosgosstrakh”, Sberbank, or other employers.

Step 3: an enhanced study of foreign languages by students. It is necessary to make language courses “cross-cutting”, i.e., measurements in each semester of training in the “classical” bachelor's degree so that some of the senior courses can be mastered in a foreign language. An example of useful innovations is the Higher School of Economics: in the bachelor's program

in spatial “Economics” there are 22 (!) subjects in English - from “International Trade” to “Theory of Probability and Statistics”. A positive example of the Novosibirsk State University is the opening of the Russian-language Master's program in Quantitative Economics jointly with the University “Paris I - Sorbonne Panthéon”.

Step 4: foreign languages - for teachers, compulsory reading of 20-30% of the “classical” bachelor's courses in foreign languages. Most university professors (especially non-capital ones) do not speak foreign languages at a level sufficient to give lectures and conduct seminars on their subjects. Inviting foreign experts is very expensive. It is necessary to select the most purposeful, promising associate professors and professors in the group of in-depth study of foreign languages (for 1–2 years). The case for people should have a clear financial motivation - a penny increase in the distant future is unlikely to interest anyone.

Step 5: Intensification of training in the magistracy and increasing the demands on the research component. It is necessary to extend the term of study in the master's program to 1–1.5 years by clarifying the work plans for applicants with specialized education (recall, Oxford University's master's program takes only one year). For applicants with non-core education, it is worth increasing the period of study by an additional 1–1.5 years to form a sufficient theoretical base in a new field for them. Instead of deepening and expanding “bachelor's knowledge”, teachers need to have time to

⁸ Among them, the author would include the disciplines taught in one of the leading metropolitan universities – “Fundamentals of the Welfare State”, “Model of Man in Economics” and several others. In addition, often similar information is contained in different disciplines, for example,

“Strategic financial management”, “Financial management”, etc. Reading the same material, which artificially “inflates” the program, should not be allowed.

explain the basics of science to qualified, but "non-core" undergraduates.

It is also necessary to increase the demands on master's theses - the mandatory placement of abstracts on the websites of universities, it is necessary to indicate the requirement for the presence of at least one scientific article in publications included in a special list of the Higher Attestation Commission. The latter will be evidence of the achievement of a certain scientific level by the undergraduate. It seems important to increase the share of courses taught in a foreign language - up to 30-40%. Perhaps to receive a prestigious education and the prestige of a master's degree of prestige from distance learning.

Step 6: organization of a functioning system of student academic mobility. The best senior students must have the opportunity to create internships in a foreign language in one of the included universities in Russia for one semester, which will be a significant incentive for the qualitative study of foreign languages.

It should be noted that the complication of training programs will inevitably cause an outflow of applicants, most likely, in the use of an applied bachelor's degree. Is it bad? By no means, for example, in Soviet times, the number of student universities was significantly less than in modern Russia (Fig. 2).

Table 4.

Information on the number of students and the number of universities in the Russian Empire, the Soviet Union, and Russia in 1914–2022

Periods	Number of higher education institutions (universities)			Number of students (thousand people)		
	Russian Empire	USSR	Russian Federation	Russian Empire	USSR	Russian Federation
1914	500	-	-	70	-	-
1917	1000	-	-	90	-	-
1927	-	700	-	-	30	-
1940-1941	-	3200	-	-	500	-
1950-1951	-	3300	-	-	800	-
1960-1961	-	2800	-	-	1500	-
1980-1981	-	3100	-	-	3100	-
1990-1991	-	3200	-	-	2800	-
1995-1996	-	-	5100	-	-	2750
2008-2009	-	-	7100	-	-	7300
2000-2001	-	-	6250	-	-	4600
2013-2014	-	-	7100	-	-	6100
2017-2018	-	-	7200	-	-	5900
2020-2021	-	-	7150	-	-	6100
2021-2022	-	-	6600	-	-	6500

(Source [8])

The development of an applied undergraduate institute is quite in line with Bologna's acceptability, emphasizing "the importance of education and educational cooperation in the development and strengthening of sustainable, global and democratic societies." With the active introduction of an applied bachelor's degree, most people will have a higher mass education. At the same time, the most talented and gifted in the professional field must master complex programs with mandatory foreign components.

For the formation of analytical and research competencies, it will be necessary to conduct additional training in even more complicated master's programs. It is the objective complexity and laboriousness of obtaining "new diplomas" that should significantly raise the prestige of modern Russian higher education.

Conclusions. Russia's accession to the Bologna Declaration did not cause significant negative consequences; it cannot be denied. However, the positive impact cannot be considered significant. The reason is that it is impossible to correct many of the shortcomings of the Russian education system solely by joining the Bologna process - it simply does not concern them. At the

same time, the introduction of a multi-stage system of higher education allows for more "fine-tuning", but in Russia, this was limited to a mechanistic separation of undergraduate and graduate courses. It was necessary to significantly intensify the educational processes in the "classical" bachelor's and master's programs, enrich them with the reading of disciplines in foreign languages, and increase the demands on students and teachers with a corresponding salary adjustment. The rejection of the Bologna system and the return to the former system, which is outdated, still does not exclude the need for reforms.

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